

Initial georeferenced groundtruth datasets include:

- United States ([link](#));
- Argentina (data from the Water Resources Management of Córdoba Province (APRHI) [link](#) and Mendoza Province [link](#));
- Nigeria (Principal Investigator's dataset covering [60,000 reference points](#));
- Italy irrigation data from [Cedar Anbi Lombardia](#) and the [Regione Lombardia](#));
- Indo-Gangetic Basin, India ([link](#) and [link](#)), Nashik, South Central India (farmer-reported irrigation strategies for grape cultivation [link 1](#), [link 2](#), and [link 3](#));
- Brazil ([National Water Agency irrigation database](#)), Brazil data provided by state (<https://agricultura.sp.gov.br/>, <https://www.agricultura.rs.gov.br/>), and federal agencies (<https://www.embrapa.br/>, <https://www.gov.br/ana/>, <https://www.snirh.gov.br/>, <https://www.gov.br/mdr/>) as well as private organizations (<https://www.aspipp.com.br/>, <https://irrigoias.com.br/>).